

LIVER ACTIVITY, DISEASES AND DISEASE PREVENTION

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Annotation. The article focuses on the liver, one of the internal organs of living organisms. The liver is one of the largest organisms in the body. It helps digest food, synthesizes the energy needed for life, and removes toxins from the body. The liver plays an important role in the production of bile, digestion and blood. In doing so, the liver uses a protected product to neutralize toxins that are formed or added to the food. If the liver fails, it will inevitably lead to death.

Keywords: liver, filter, metabolism, hepatitis, viral hepatitis, bile, toxin, energy, immunity, fibrosis.

**ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ПЕЧЕНИ, ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКА
ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ**

Аннотация. В статье речь пойдет о печени, одном из внутренних органов живых организмов. Печень является одним из крупнейших организмов в организме. Он помогает переваривать пищу, синтезирует энергию, необходимую для жизни, и выводит токсины из организма. Печень играет важную роль в производстве желчи, пищеварении и крови. При этом печень использует защищенный продукт для нейтрализации токсинов, которые образуются или добавляются в пищу. Если печень откажет, это неизбежно приведет к смерти.

Ключевые слова: печень, фильтр, обмен веществ, гепатит, вирусный гепатит, желчь, токсин, энергия, иммунитет, фиброз.

Introduction. Location of the liver - Most of the liver is located in the right subcostal area, and the lower edge of the normal liver does not extend beyond the rib cage. The liver is one of the largest digestive glands in the body and weighs up to 1,500 grams.

Theoretical Basis. The function of the liver is to convert nutrients that are harmful to the body into chemicals by the liver. Filters out all harmful substances and converts consumed food into energy. Mild liver dysfunction can affect the whole body. There are many reasons for this, for example: the immune system protects our body from various bacteria and viruses. If you have the hepatitis virus in your liver and you drink a lot of alcohol, you are more prone to liver cancer. Liver disease progresses slowly, so the symptoms should be carefully monitored as the liver is the largest organ in the body that needs care. Harmful habits should be avoided in maintaining liver health. For example, smoking cessation - the toxic substances of tobacco smoke enter the liver, and instead of performing its normal function, the liver is engaged in clearing the blood of tobacco toxins. As a result, liver cells and arteries are damaged. Maintaining the health of the liver is responsible for the proper functioning of the whole organism, and most importantly, the liver is one of the organs capable of regenerating itself.

Changes in the body in diseases of the liver - For example, liver serosal.

Results. Cirrhosis of the liver is a chronic disease of the organ caused by the irreversible replacement of liver parenchymal tissue with fibrous connective tissue or stroma. The cirrhotic liver is enlarged or reduced in size, unusually dense, and concave. Mortality occurs in the terminal stage within 2–4 years, depending on different conditions, with the patient experiencing severe pain and suffering. liver cirrhosis is one of the 6 leading causes of death in patients aged 35-60 years, accounting for 14-30 cases per 100,000 population. Every year, 40 million people worldwide die from viral liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma due to the transmission of hepatitis B virus. In the CIS countries, the disease occurs in 1% of the population.

Discussion. Common symptoms of cirrhosis:

- Weakness, decreased ability to work;
- Unpleasant feelings in the abdomen;
- Dyspeptic disorders;
- Rising body temperature;
- Joint pain;
- Flatulence, pain and heaviness in the upper abdomen;

- Weight loss;
- Asthenia.

Diagnosis

- Biochemical analysis of blood (ALT, ASTO)
- Angiography of dilated and branched venous collaterals
- Computed tomography
- Ultrasound examination
- Liver MRI if necessary
- Liver dopplerometry can be performed.

Prevention.

Among the preventive measures of liver cirrhosis can be included any approaches aimed at preventing the spread of hepatitis. It is also recommended to:

- Treatment of hepatitis with the help of a qualified hepatologist and adherence to the prescribed therapeutic regimen;
- Restrict arbitrary intake of drugs;
- Take vitamin and mineral complexes on the advice of a doctor;
- Do not eat fatty, fried and spicy, canned and semi-finished products;
- Refuse bad habits, especially alcohol abuse;
- Annual endoscopic examination of the digestive system;
- Observance of personal hygiene and use of personal hygiene products;
- Vaccination against viral hepatitis B.

References

1. *F.N. Bahodirov „Odam anatomiyasi ”// Toshkent 2005.*
2. *Vengerovskiy.Al. Jigar tizimini tartibga solishda farmakologik tuzlar/ Al Venherovskiy// Axborotnomasi Sibir tibbiyoti. -2002- yil.*
3. *Roitberg G.E. Ichki jigar yo'llari, jigar osti bezi: o'quv qo'llanma/ G.E. Roitberg. A.V Strutynskiy/M.: MED press-inform,2016.*
4. *Polina T.E Jigarining tibbiy zararlanishi/Gastroenterologiya-2011.*
5. *Xaligi T.R. Jigar tadqiqotlari, klinik va klinik-onkologik tadqiqotlar/ Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti. Moskva, 2012- yil.*